

A Comprehensive Checklist of Orchids Diversity in Western Himalayas of Azad Kashmir, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

A checklist comprised 32 species of orchids recorded from the Western Himalayas of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. The best-represented genus is *Habenaria* with six species, followed by *Epipactis* with five species, *Dactylorhiza* with three species, and *Neottia* and *Malaxis* with two species. In the current study, extensive field surveys were conducted from 2020 to 2022, from the subtropics to the subalpine zones of the study area. Data was collected from 57 sites in the study area; allied flora was also studied, along with orchids. The most orchid species were found in the divisions of Poonch and Muzaffarabad. Under the guidance of an expert taxonomist, specimens were identified using the flora of Pakistan, China, India, and Azad Jammu and Kashmir, as well as by comparing them to specimens from the AKASH herbarium. Under the guidance of an expert taxonomist, specimens were identified using the flora of Pakistan, China, India, and Azad Jammu and Kashmir, as well as by comparing them to specimens from the AKASH herbarium. Flowering habit, habitat, endemic status, and distribution in the study area are presented in the checklist.

Keywords: Orchids, Checklist, Western Himalayas, Taxonomist.

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INTRODUCTION

Orchidaceae is the world's second-largest family of angiosperms, with 870 genera and about 25,000 species (Swarts and Dixon 2009; Rao et al. 2012). Orchids are found in tropical, subtropical, and temperate climates but are most common in humid tropical climates (Misra 2007, Singh et al. 2001). Surface under forest trees, forest vegetation, riverbanks, forest floor, grassy slopes, and rocky regions as their preferred environment (Zhang et al. 2015). Furthermore, they are not habitat-specific; they require certain micro-climatic environmental conditions to develop and live within a habitat. They like sufficient moisture and shady habitats in terrestrial conditions; for

example, they are most active during the rainy season (Jalal & Rawat, 2009). The Himalayas are one of the world's most biodiverse regions (Mittermeier et al., 2005) and are well-known for having a diverse array of orchids (Pant, 2013, 2010, Jalal & Jayanthi, 2015). Overall, it is estimated that more than 850 species of orchids exist in the Himalayan region (Acharya et al. 2011).

In Pakistan, 26 genera and 47 orchid species have been reported so far (Nasir and Ali, 2008). In India, 1331 orchid species belonging to 186 genera have been identified so far Mishra (2007). Orchid blooms come in a broad variety of sizes, shapes, and colours. They are a highly advanced monocot family, characterized by distinct floral morphology, small seeds, mycorrhizal association, and pollination mechanisms (Abraham, 1981). Orchids have long been prized for their therapeutic properties. As early as 200 BC, the Chinese are thought to have been the first to produce, describe, and use orchids (Singh and Duggal, 2009). Orchids have faced greater dangers in recent eras due to their aesthetic appeal and economic usefulness (Hedge, 1997). The orchids of Azad Jammu and Kashmir are threatened by several issues. Threats to orchids include overharvesting for ornamental purposes, medicinal usage, illegal trafficking, deforestation, haphazard road construction, overgrazing, forest fires, and climate change. Concerns need to be addressed for the protection of orchids, such as vigorous enforcement of current legislation and raising awareness in local communities. To protect the variety of orchids found in Azad Jammu and Kashmir, it is recommended that we develop a strong and effective conservation strategy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Azad Jammu and Kashmir has a land size of 5134 square kilometres and is located between 73°-75° longitude and 33°-36° latitude. The environment is rugged, with deep holes and rough, never-ending terrain. The climate of Azad Jammu and Kashmir varies according to height (360 m in the south to 6,325 m in the north). It has a subtropical climate that ranges from dry in the south to humid in the north. The average rainfall is between 1,000 and 2,000 mm. Snow accounts for 30 to 60% of precipitation in mountain locations. The lowest temperature in the region ranges from 20°C to 32°C and from 04°C to 07°C (GoAJK, 2013; Altaf and Umair, 2022.). Figure 1: Geographical location of the study area.

DATA COLLECTION

Several field studies were conducted in different bioclimatic zones of the study area from 2020 to 2022 (Figure 1). Field notes were recorded along with sample documents for each species observed using standard methods (Jain and Rau 1977). . The specimens were identified using flora of Pakistan (Swart, 1972; Nasir and Ali, 1970-1992; Ali and Qaiser, 1993-2019), the flora of China, flora of India, and compared to species from AKASH herbarium in Azad Jammu and Kashmir University under the supervision of expert taxonomist. Accepted names are italicized, and boldfaced, and basonyms are also italicized. Dressler's classification system is used to organize the list (1993). The authors' names are cited

by following Brummitt and Powell, 1992). After the author's citation, each species' habitat has been recorded. A collector number is assigned to each species. The voucher specimens were deposited at the AKASH Herbarium University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

Figure 1: Geographical location of the study area.

RESULTS

The current study identified 19 genera and 32 orchid species from Azad Jammu and Kashmir. *Habenaria* is the largest genus with 6 species followed by *Epipactis* with 5 species *Dactylorhiza* with 3 species and *Neottia* and *Malaxis* with 2 species (Table 1). Following is a taxonomy summary of all orchid species. The scientific name of each species, bibliography, basionym and synonyms (if applicable), characteristics, flowering time, regional distribution (including regional distribution) and height and meter are all included. *Dactylorhiza hatagirea* and *Dactylorhiza kafiriana* perennial herbaceous plants species were collected from Shounter Valley elevation of 3000 m -3097 m. *Dactylorhiza* species are preferred to grow in moist conditions, most of the members of this genus were collected from (marshes) bank of Shounter Nullah. *Cypripedium cordigerum* preferred to grow under the shade of *Abies pindrow*, *Taxus wallichiana* and showed a close relationship with *Viburnum grandiflorum*. *Cymbidium macrorhizon* found association with *Pinus*

wallichiana and *Pinus roxburghii*. plant favor moist and shady place where leaf litter found in large amount. *Satyrium nepalense* identified from site Malak District Bagh at altitudinal range 1630m south facing aspect found in association with *Punica granatum* and *Pinus wallichiana*. *Habenaria aitchisonii* preferred to grow in soil rich in organic matter and leaf litter. Orchid showed association with *Taxus wallichiana* and *Abies pindrow*. Orchids are not habitat-specific, within a habitat, they require specific micro-climatic environmental conditions to grow and survive. For example, they favor sufficient moisture and shady environments in terrestrial conditions and usually appear during the rainy season.

DISCUSSION

The finding of this study describes Azad Jammu and Kashmir as a floristically important area with a high diversity of plants. The degree of disturbance each population experienced in their specific habitat determined the number of orchids and their ability to survive in the disturbed forests. The findings indicate that compared to heavily disturbed logging sites, secondary woods that had undergone just minor disturbances had a higher density of orchids. This was unquestionably caused by the environmental changes brought on by anthropogenic perturbations. In particular, temperature, humidity, precipitation, and light intensity, as well as the existence of supporting trees and organisms like fungus, mosses, and pollinators, were related to these fluctuations (Cribb et al. 2003; Cozzolino and Widmer 2005). In contrast, the secondary forests' habitat conditions (moisture and nutrient availability) were still favourable for the growth of both epiphytic and terrestrial orchids, indicating a healthier environment for orchid survival. The trees were essential for aiding in the photosynthesis, pollination, and reproduction of orchids (Bergman et al., 2006).

Ethnomedicinally, plants have been used as traditional ethnomedicine by the ancient civilization of human beings for managing various diseases (Amjad et al., 2020; Hamid et al., 2021; Imtiaz et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2017; Saeed et al., 2022; Imtiaz et al., 2023). It is believed that the Chinese were the first ones to describe medicinal uses of orchids in the treatment of different diseases, for example, Sang Nung pen Tsao ching recommended orchids as a source of analgesic, tonic, astringent, and anti-inflammatory drugs (Bulpitt, 2005; Saeed et al., 2022). Jivanti and Rasna are common drugs of orchid origin (Bulpitt et al., 2007). Recent studies showed that orchids have medicinally important molecules that help reduce fever, improve white blood cell numbers, cure eye disease, are useful against fatigue and headache, and are among the best uses against cancer. Orchids have long been used in traditional medicines as anti-inflammatory agents and fertility boosters (Jalal, 2005). Orchids are very effective against various stomach, germ cell, and lungs cancer (Ho and Chen, 2003). Orchids are also treat flatulence, rheumatism, spasm, and epilepsy. They are also used in sedative medicines, increase fertility, and are flavor enhancers (Ho and Chen, 2003; Amjad et al., 2020).

CONCLUSION

The current study shows a checklist of orchids found at western Himalayas Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Pakistan. 32 orchids species were reported from study area. This

is a baseline study for orchid diversity in the study area. Studies showed that orchid species favoured moist and shady places where organic matter available.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The corresponding author will have access to the study's data upon request.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Karamit Hussain designed the Research field work and collection and Identification of the Samples orchid plants. Muhammad Ejaz Ul Islam Dar Supervised and Hamayun Shaheen Cosupervised. Shakeel Sabir Assisted in drawing and reviewing the draft, Tariq Habib, and Ansar Mehmood Reviewed the Final Draft, and Taskeen Iqbal, Arshad Mehmood Khan and Muhammad Shakeel Awan helped with editing and proofreading.

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Table 1: The checklist of Orchids reported from different localities of Azad Jammu and Kashmir

Voucher Number	Bar code	Species name	Habit and habitat	Flowering period	Distribution
5101	AKASH005001	<i>Calanthe plantaginea</i> Lindley	1500–2000 m above sea level, terrestrial, subtropical to temperate regions	March – April.	Pakistan, India, Nepal and Bhutan; Jammu, Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Bagh)
5102	AKASH005002	<i>Cephalanthera longifolia</i> Fritsch	Terrestrial, 1800–2500 m, subtropical to temperate regions	May – July.	Europe, northern Africa, temperate Asia; Kashmir (Machira National Park)
5103	AKASH005003	<i>Cymbidium macrorhizon</i> Lindl.	Mycoheterotrophy, subtropical region, 800 – 2000 m.	June – July.	From Pakistan eastwards to Assam and Burma, the Khasia Hills and Thailand, Kashmir (Danna Muzaffarabad)
5104	AKASH005004	<i>Cypripedium cordigerum</i> D. Don	Terrestrial, in the temperate zone, at 2000–3000 m.	May – June.	Pakistan, India, Nepal, Bhutan, China; Jammu (Poonch), Kashmir (Machira National Park)
5105	AKASH005005	<i>Dactylorhiza hatagirea</i> D. Don	Terrestrial, 3000–4000 m, subalpine to alpine zone.	June – July.	Nepal, Bhutan, China, Pakistan, Jammu (Poonch), and Kashmir (Shooter Neelum Valley)
5106	AKASH005006	<i>Dactylorhiza kafiriana</i> Renz.	Terrestrial, alpine marshy meadows, 1700 – 4200 m.	June – July.	In Pakistan on its northern border region (Chitral, Gilgit, Hunza) in high altitude marshes, Azad Kashmir (Shounter Neelum Valley)
5107	AKASH005007	<i>Dactylorhiza viridis</i> Lind.	Terrestrial, alpine region, 3000 – 4000 m.	July – August.	Pakistan, India, Bhutan, China, Europe, Central Asia, and Kashmir (Shooter

Voucher Number	Bar code	Species name	Habit and habitat	Flowering period	Distribution
5108	AKASH005008	<i>Dienia cylindrostachya</i> Revis.	Terrestrial, temperate to alpine regions, 2200 – 3500 m.	July – August.	Neelum Valley) India, Bhutan, China; Azad Kashmir (Brathwar Gali site Leepa valley),
5109	AKASH005009	<i>Epipactis helleborine</i> Stirp.	Terrestrial, 1000–4000 m, subtropical to alpine regions	July – August.	Europe, Northern Africa, Japan, Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Lakhi Jungle Muzaffarabad), Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, and Bhutan
5110	AKASH005010	<i>Epipactis persica</i> 1946 Soó.	Terrestrial, subtropical to alpine regions, 1000 – 3500 m.	July – August.	Iran, Afghanistan, Pakistan and India; July-August and Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Dhirkot)
5111	AKASH005011	<i>Epipactis royleana</i> Gen.	Terrestrial, subtropical to temperate regions, 1000 – 3500 m	July – August.	China, Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Nepal, Bhutan, Afghanistan, Pakistan, and India (Lawat Neelum Valley)
5112	AKASH005012	<i>Epipactis veratrifolia</i> Diagn	Terrestrial, subtropical region, 500 – 2500 m.	Februray – March.	Pakistan, Nepal, Myanmar, India and China, Afghanistan; Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Mehmood Gali Haveli)
5113	AKASH005013	<i>Epipactis gigantea</i> Dougl.	Terrestrial, temperate to alpine regions, 2500 – 4000 m.	July – August.	Himalaya Nepal, Sikkim Bhutan; China and Central America. (Kasyian Ryat site Muzaffarabad)
5114	AKASH005014	<i>Epipogium roseum</i> D. Don	Mycoheterotrophic, subtropical to subalpine regions, 600 – 3000 m.	August – September.	India; Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Sangar Bagh)

Voucher Number	Bar code	Species name	Habit and habitat	Flowering period	Distribution
5115	AKASH005015	<i>Goodyera repens</i> L.	Terrestrial, 2000–3600 m, temperate to subalpine areas.	July – August.	Asia, Europe, North America, India, Bhutan, Myanmar, China, Japan, Pakistan and Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Nakar Haveli).
5116	AKASH005016	<i>Gymnadenia orchidis</i> L.	Terrestrial, subalpine to alpine regions, 3000 – 4500 m.	July – August	Pakistan, India, Bhutan and China; and Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Peer Chanasi Muzaffrabad)
5117	AKASH005017	<i>Habenaria aitchisonii</i> Aitchison & Hemsl.	Terrestrial, temperate to subalpine regions, 2000 – 4000 m.	July – August.	Pakistan, India and Nepal; and Azad Jammu & Kashmir (Arang Kail Neelum Valley)
5118	AKASH005018	<i>Habenaria digitata</i> Gen.	Terrestrial, subtropics, Temperate to sub alpine region c. 1500 -3200m	July – August.	Pakistan and India; Azad Kashmir (Sankhra Bagh)
5119	AKASH005019	<i>Habenaria furcifera</i> Gen.	Terrestrial, subtropical, temperate and sub alpine region at an altitude 1500- 3200 m.	July – August.	Pakistan, India and Bhutan, Azad Kashmir (Toli peer poonch)
5120	AKASH005020	<i>Habenaria intermedia</i> D. Don	Terrestrial, temperate to subalpine regions, 2000 – 2700 m.	July – August.	Pakistan and India; Azad Kashmir (Shero Dahra District haveli)
5121	AKASH005021	<i>Herminium monorchis</i> L.	Terrestrial, subtropics, temperate and subalpine regions, 1500– 3500 m.	July – August.	Pakistan, India, China, Korea, Japan; Azad Kashmir (Gudgar Haveli)

Voucher Number	Bar code	Species name	Habit and habitat	Flowering period	Distribution
5122	AKASH005022	<i>Liparis rostrata</i> Reichenbach	1500–2500 m above sea level, terrestrial, subtropical to temperate regions	July – August.	Pakistan, India; Azad Kashmir (SheroDhara Haveli)
5123	AKASH005023	<i>Malaxis muscifera</i> Lindley	Terrestrial, 1800–3500 m, temperate to subalpine areas.	July – August.	Pakistan, India, Bhutan, China; Azad Kashmir (Manji Shaheed site District Haveli)
5124	AKASH005024	<i>Neottia inayatii</i> Duthie	Mycoheterotrophic, moist temperate to subalpine regions. 2000-3000 m.	July.	Pakistan, China Nepal, Azad Kashmir (Brathwar Gali Leepa valley).
5125	AKASH005025	<i>Neottia listeroides</i> Lindley	Moist, temperate to subalpine environments, between 2000 and 3500 m.	July – September.	Pakistan, India, Myanmar, China; Azad Kashmir (Daokhan site Leepa Valley).
5126	AKASH005026	<i>Nervilia gammieana</i> Hooker	Terrestrial, subtropical region, 600-1600 m.	May – June.	Pakistan, India; Azad Kashmir (Chamber Haveli).
5127	AKASH005027	<i>Oreorchis foliosa</i> Lindley	Terrestrial, temperate to subalpine regions, 2500 – 3500 m.	June – July.	India, Pakistan, Bhutan; Azad Kashmir (Machiara site District Muzaffarabad).
5128	AKASH005028	<i>Platanthera edgeworthii</i> Hooker	Temperate to subalpine region, 1500 – 3000 m	July – August.	Pakistan, India and Nepal; Azad Kashmir (Rawalakot).
5129	AKASH005029	<i>Platanthera latilabris</i> Lindley	Land-based, subtropical to temperate climates, 1500–3000 m above sea level.	July – August.	Pakistan, India, Nepal and Bhutan; Azad Kashmir (Baikri Danna District Muzaffarabad)

Voucher Number	Bar code	Species name	Habit and habitat	Flowering period	Distribution
5130	AKASH005030	<i>Satyrium nepalense</i> D. Don	Terrestrial, 2000–3000 m, temperate to subalpine zones.	July – August.	Pakistan, India, Nepal, Bhutan, China; Azad Kashmir (Malak District Bagh).
5131	AKASH005031	<i>Spiranthes sinensis</i> Persoon	Terrestrial, 1600–3500 m, subtropical to subalpine area.	May – September.	Afghan Kashmir (Sudhan Gali chakra location District Jehlum), Pakistan, India, Java, Nepal, China, Australia, New Zealand, Japan, Europe and North America.
5132	AKASH005032	<i>Zeuxine strateumatica</i> L.	Terrestrial, tropical to subtropical regions, 500 – 1500m.	March – April.	Iran, Pakistan, India, Nepal, Myanmar, China, Japan